

VIRTUAL TEXTILE COMPOSITES SOFTWARE WISETEX: INTEGRATION WITH MICRO- MECHANICAL, PERMEABILITY AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

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SUMMARY: Internal geometry of textile reinforcement is an important factor of the reinforcement performance during the composite manufacturing and in the service life of the composite material. When a 3D shaped composite part is concerned, the reinforced is locally deformed (compressed, stretched and sheared), and the geometrical model should account for this deformation. The software package *WiseTex* implements a generalised description of internal structure of textile reinforcement on the unit cell level, integrated with mechanical models of relaxed and deformed state of 2D and 3D woven, two- and three-axial braided, weft-knitted and non-crimp warp-knit stitched fabrics and laminates. It is integrated with modelling of resin flow, micro-mechanical calculations of properties of composite and micro-macro analysis of composite parts, finite element models and virtual reality software. The paper describes this family of models, which use a unified description of the geometry of the reinforcement unit cell.

KEYWORDS: Textile composites; meso-modelling; internal geometry; permeability; micro-mechanics; finite elements; multi-level analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The internal geometry of a textile reinforcement is an important factor of the reinforcement performance during composite manufacturing and in service life of the composite material. For the former, impregnation of the reinforcement is governed by its porosity (size, distribution and connectivity of pores). For the latter, load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement is governed by the fibre orientation, which plays a paramount role in the composite stiffness; stress-strain concentration loci, determining the composite strength, are correlated with the resin rich zones and fibre/matrix interfaces, distributed in the composite

volume in accordance with the reinforcement geometry. When a 3D shaped composite part is concerned, the reinforcement is locally deformed (compressed, stretched and sheared), and the geometrical model should account for this deformation.

A generalised description of the internal structure of a textile reinforcement has been developed in K.U.Leuven. It is integrated with mechanical models of the relaxed and deformed state of 2D and 3D woven [1-4], two- and three-axial braided [5], weft-knitted [6]

Figure 1 Data transfer in WiseTex family of software

and non-crimp warp-knit stitched [7] fabrics and laminates [8]. The models are implemented in a software package *WiseTex*, and are integrated with modelling of resin flow through the reinforcement [9,10], micro-mechanical calculations of properties of the composite [1,2] and micro-macro analysis of the composite parts [11,12], finite element models [13-17] and virtual

reality software [18,19] (Table 1 and Figure 1). All these models use a unified description of the geometry of the reinforcement unit cell. The present paper summarises these developments, with an aim to facilitate its future use of the unified textile models by other researchers.

Table 1 *WiseTex* family of software

	<i>Purpose</i>	<i>Developed by, reference</i>
<i>WiseTex</i>	Internal geometry of textiles in relaxed state Compression, tension and shear of the textile	Lomov et al, K.U.Leuven [1-5, 20]
<i>LamTex</i>	Internal geometry of textile laminates	Lomov et al, K.U.Leuven [8]
<i>FETex</i>	Convertor of <i>WiseTex</i> data into FE description	Lomov et al, K.U.Leuven [14]
<i>MeshTex</i>	Convertor of <i>WiseTex</i> data into FE description (SACOM)	Zako et al, Osaka University [17]
<i>TexComp</i>	Stiffness properties of a textile composite, inclusion model	Huysmans et al, K.U.Leuven [21,22]
<i>FlowTex</i>	Permeability of textile, lattice Boltzmann/finite difference	Belov, Peeters et al, K.U.Leuven [9]
<i>Celper</i>	Permeability of textile, finite elements, voxel discretization	Laine, Boust et al, ONERA [10]
<i>VRTex</i>	Virtual reality of textiles on meso-level	Mikolanda et al, T.U.Librec [18,19]

UNIFIED DESCRIPTION OF GEOMETRY OF UNIT CELL AND ITS TRANSLATION TO FE MODELS

The geometrical and mechanical model of textiles, implemented in the software package *WiseTex*, provides full description of the internal geometry of a fabric: 2D and 3D woven, two- and three-axial braided, knitted, multi-axial multi-ply stitched (non-crimp fabric). Input data include: (1) Yarn properties: geometry of the cross-section, compression, bending, frictional and tensile behaviour, fibrous content; (2) Yarn interlacing pattern; (3) Yarn spacing within the fabric repeat. Models for compression, bi- and uniaxial tension and shear are also based on energy balance and calculate internal structure of the deformed fabric, as well as load-deformation relation. The description of the internal geometry is unified both for deformed and undeformed fabrics. This section explains this description and algorithms of its conversion into FE models. The reader is referred to the papers cited above for full formulation and experimental validation of the *WiseTex* models.

Yarns

Description of the yarns geometry in the textile modelling software

Consider a fabric consisting of yarns only (fibrous plies in NCF are discussed below). Figure 2 illustrates the description of the spatial configuration of the yarns. The midline of a yarn is given by the spatial positions of the centres of the yarn cross-sections O : $\mathbf{r}(s)$, where s is coordinate along the midline, \mathbf{r} is the radius-vector of the point O . Let $\mathbf{t}(s)$ be the tangent to the midline at the point O . The cross-section of the yarn, normal to \mathbf{t} , is defined by its dimensions $d_1(s)$ and $d_2(s)$ along axis $\mathbf{a}_1(s)$ and $\mathbf{a}_2(s)$. These axes are “glued” with the cross-section and rotate around $\mathbf{t}(s)$, if the yarn is twisted along its path (such a twist can be the result of the fabric shearing [5]). Because of this rotation the system $[\mathbf{a}_1\mathbf{a}_2\mathbf{t}]$ may differ from the natural coordinate system along the spatial path $[\mathbf{n}\mathbf{b}\mathbf{t}]$. The shape of the cross-section can be assumed elliptical, lenticular etc. The shape type does not change along the yarn, but dimensions d_1 and d_2 can change because of different compression of the yarn in the contact zones and between them. Definition of the spatial positions of a yarn with a given cross-section shape in a unit cell consists therefore of five periodic functions: $\mathbf{r}(s)$ (then $[\mathbf{n}\mathbf{b}\mathbf{t}]$ vectors can be calculated), $\mathbf{a}_1(s)$, $\mathbf{a}_2(s)$, $d_1(s)$, $d_2(s)$. These functions are calculated for all the yarns in the unit cell by a geometrical model. When used in numerical calculations, all these functions are given as arrays of values for a set of points along the yarn midline.

Figure 2 Set of cross-sections defining a yarn in a unit cell, properties of fibres near point P; Meshing of the yarns: two elements with penetrating mesh; separation and “compression”; mesh of the unit cell, no penetration

This description fully defines the volumes of the yarns in a unit cell. The format is the same for orthogonal and non-orthogonal (angle α , Figure 2) unit cells. The in-plane dimensions of the unit cell X , Y are given by the repeat size of the textile structure, whereas the thickness Z is calculated as the difference between the maximum and minimum z -coordinates of the cross-sections of all the yarns in the unit cell. To describe the fibrous structure of the unit cell, consider a point P and fibrous assembly in the vicinity of this point (Figure 2). The fibrous assembly can be characterised by physical and mechanical parameters of the fibres near the point (which are not necessarily the same in all points of the fabric), fibre volume fraction V_f and direction \mathbf{f} of them. If the point does not lie inside a yarn, then $V_f=0$ and \mathbf{f} is not defined. For a point inside a yarn, the fibrous properties are easily calculated, providing that the fibrous structure of the yarns in the virgin state and its dependency of local compression, bending and twisting of the yarn are given. Consider a point P . Searching the cross-sections of

the yarns, the cross-sections S_i and S_{i+1} , containing between their planes the point P, are found (binary search in the unit cell volume is employed to speed up the calculations), and then by interpolation, the cross-section S, which plane contains the point P, is built. Using the dimensions of the cross-section S, for a given shape of it, point P is identified as lying inside or outside the yarn. In the former case, with the position of the point P inside the yarn known, using the model of the yarn microstructure, the parameters of fibrous assembly in the vicinity of the point P are calculated.

Translation to finite element model: Woven reinforcements

The geometry of the yarn volumes can be easily transferred to a finite element description. A section of a yarn between neighbouring cross-sections is subdivided into four volumes (or kept intact if $d_2/d_1 > 5$). An assembly of these volumes constitutes a solid model of the fabric. For all the yarns a transversal isotropic material model is used, the properties of the impregnated yarns calculated using local fibre volume fraction and fibre orientation in the yarns (assumed constant within one segment between two neighboring cross-sections).

The yarn volumes are effectively meshed, using a “sweep” meshing operation: a mesh built on the first cross-section of the yarn is being “swept” through the yarn, creating a quite regular mesh. Building a mesh inside matrix is more challenging proposition. Mesh in the yarns can penetrate one another due to approximations in the geometrical model (Figure 2). To eliminate the penetration, yarn elements are first separated, with a resistant media placed between them, and then compressed together, so that the edges get to the initial position. the resulting mesh has no penetrations [16,17].

Fibrous plies

Description of the plies geometry in the textile modelling software

The description of the geometry of multi-axial multi-ply stitched preforms (also called “non-crimp fabrics”, NCF) includes the geometry of the stitching yarns and geometry of the fibrous plies [7].

Figure 3 Quadriaxial NCF, orientation of the fibres in the plies 0°/-45°/90°/45°. (a) Full geometrical model with stitching. Note a “channel” in the first 0° ply; (b) “cracks” in the -45° ply; (c) Channels/cracks width in cross-sections of the composite plate, thick white lines show width of the cracks as computed by the model, section in the cross-direction, channel in the 0° face ply and a crack in the -45° inner ply; (d) Slab representation of a ply with -45° “cracks”. ABCDEF – vertices of the upper polygon of one of the slabs;

Figure 4 Automatic meshing process. (a) Hexaedral finite elements created by sweeping operation;. (b) Tetrahedral mesh built in the transition region; (c) Composite surface at the interface between plies; (d) 2D mesh at the interface.

The stitching, even thin, interacts with the fibrous plies, which are unidirectional arrays of fibres with approximately constant thickness. The stitching causes deviations of the fibres in a ply from their uniform directions. These deviations produce fibre-free zones near stitching locations, which are regularly spaced over the ply. The fibre-free zones can be local (and called "openings" below), or can form continuous channels in the ply (Figure 3). The local fibre volume fraction in a ply is increased and voids are created as a result of the stitching.

The width and length of the "cracks" and "channels" should be measured or calculated with empirical formulae based on dimensions of the stitching yarn (Lomov *et al.* 2002). When sheared, the fibre density in the plies increases, and the width of the "cracks" and "channels" decreases. After shear angle of 30° the width reaches its minimum. This change of the width in shear is described by empirical formulae [23]. The complex geometry of a fibrous ply with "openings" and "channels" is represented in the *WiseTex* model as a set of "slabs". A slab is a volume formed by two parallel polygons. Vertices of all the slabs are stored in the counter-clockwise order (Figure 3d).

Translation to finite element model: Non-crimp fabrics

The translation to FE model is done in the following steps [15]: an automatic procedure is used to generate a continuous model satisfying the compatibility conditions and, finally, resulting meshes on boundary surfaces is built as to have matching node patterns in order for periodic boundary conditions to be applied in analysis.

Surfaces generated at the geometry decomposition stage are meshed using quadrilateral elements, and resulting mesh is projected (swept) through the thickness direction, thus obtaining regular hexahedral elements (Figure 4a). Meshes obtained in this way are, in general, unconnected finite element domains whose nodes do not coincide along their common boundaries. In order to preserve nodal connectivity across interface, a transition region is built by using an intermediate space to glue partitioned domains using tetrahedral elements (Figure 4b). This technique provides a useful method to satisfy the continuity and the compatibility conditions on non-conforming interfaces between consecutive plies without increasing significantly the computational cost. Finally, matching node patterns are defined on model boundaries by translating node positions along the fabric periodicity vectors. The FE model obtained in this way is suitable for applying periodic boundary conditions.

PERMEABILITY

Calculation of permeability is based on voxel representation of the unit cell volume (Figure 5a). A voxel is either empty (pore) or filled with fibres. The flow of the fluid in the pores is governed by Navier-Stokes equations (NC-voxels), inside the permeable tows – by Brinkmann equation (B-voxels). In the latter case local permeability (micro-level) is calculated with formulae of Gebart and Berdichevsky for unidirectional array of fibres. These equations are solved by numerical schemes based on lattice Boltzmann (*FlowTex* [9]), finite difference (*FlowTex* [24]) or finite element algorithms (*CELPER* [10]). Homogenised permeability of a unit cell is determined using average flux of the fluid through the unit cell under periodic boundary conditions for the given pressure difference on the unit cell facets.

Figure 5b illustrates calculation of flow through a fabric made of monofilament fibres. Precise definition of the geometry results in very good prediction of permeability: measured [25] $270 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}^2$, calculated $330 \mu\text{m}^2$ by lattice Boltzmann and $270 \mu\text{m}^2$ by finite difference method by *FlowTex*. When reinforcement with permeable tows is considered, the correct calculation of the preform compression is of major importance. Figure 5c illustrates, how *CELPER* calculations become close to the measurements, when the correct parameters of the reinforcement are chosen.

Figure 5 Calculation of permeability: (a) unit cell and voxel model; (b) Two layers of monofilament fabric: WiseTex/LamTex model and flow velocity field (FlowTex); (c) Carbon woven reinforcement: fabric, cross-section of the laminate ($V_f=55\%$), CELPER calculations with different compression of the fabric

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND DAMAGE BEHAVIOUR

Method of inclusions

To apply method of inclusions, implemented in *TexComp* software [21,22], yarns in the unit cell are subdivided into a number of smaller segments, where each yarn segment is geometrically characterised by its total volume fraction, spatial orientation, cross-sectional aspect ratio and local curvature (all these parameters are readily provided by the geometrical model). Next, Eshelby's equivalent inclusion principle is adopted to transform each heterogeneous yarn segment into homogeneity with a fictitious transformation strain distribution. The solution makes use of a short fibre equivalent, which physically reflects the drop in the axial load carrying capability of a curved yarn with respect to an initially straight yarn. Every yarn segment is hence linked to an equivalent short fibre, possessing an identical cross-sectional shape, volume fraction and orientation as the original segment it is derived from. The length of the equivalent fibre on the other hand is related to the curvature of the original yarn. For textiles with smoothly varying curvature radii, a proportional relationship between the short fibre length and the local yarn curvature radius is the most straightforward choice and sufficiently accurate for the present purpose.

Figure 6 Elastic properties of a sheared unit cell of a twill glass fabric as functions of shear angle

The interaction problem between the different reinforcing yarns is solved in the traditional way, by averaging out the image stress sampling over the different phases. If a Mori-Tanaka scheme is used, the stiffness tensor \mathbf{C}^C of the composite is hence obtained as: $\mathbf{C}^C = \left[c_m \mathbf{C}^m + \langle c_s \mathbf{C}^s \mathbf{A}^s \rangle \right] \left[c_m \mathbf{I} + \langle c_s \mathbf{A}^s \rangle \right]^{-1}$, where the subscripts m and s denote the matrix and a

yarn segment respectively, c_i is the volume fraction of phase i ($i = m, s$), and the angle brackets denote a configurational average.

As follows from this brief description, the homogenisation procedure does not depend on the configuration of the unit cell. Figure 6 illustrates the homogenisation results for a unit cell of a twill fabric glass composite for different shear angles. Such calculations are used (see below) for multi-level μ -m-M modelling of composite parts.

FE modelling of elastic and damage behaviour

The meshing procedure for woven fabrics is implemented in software *MeshTex*, which is integrated with *WiseTex*, forming a geometrical and meshing preprocessor for a finite element solver *SACOM* [17]. The data flow and FE modelling of 3D woven glass/epoxy composites is illustrated by Figure 7. Figure 8 compares results of the FE modelling of elastic deformation of woven carbon/epoxy composite with full field optical measurements [26].

Figure 7 WiseTex – MeshTex – SACOM data flow and example of FEA of 3D woven composite

Figure 8 Full field strain registration [26] on the surface of carbon-epoxy (one fabric layer) and FEA: longitudinal and transversal strain along the yarn centre line (points – experiment, lines – FEA)

The FEA of progressive damage of the stitched NCF composite was performed [13], assuming the Tsai-Hill failure criteria for the anisotropic homogenized layers. The strength parameters of the homogenized layers for Tsai-Hill domain are evaluated by the micro model assuming a transversally isotropic carbon fibre and an isotropic matrix. A simple degradation procedure, proposed by M.Zako, is applied to evaluate the damage in the layers up to complete failure. When the stress state in an element satisfies the assumed failure criterion, certain (depending of the failure mode) stiffness matrix elements are dropped down.

Figure 9 FEA of damage in NCF carbon/epoxy composites: FE model, X-ray registration of damage, strain 0.8%: calculated and measured [27,28] stress-strain diagrams with and without resin rich zone produced by the stitching; AE registration of damage. Arrows show initial damage strain (0.3%) in calculation and experiment

FEA accounts for the presence of resin-rich zones, created by the stitching. It gives good estimation of the initial damage strain, which was measured [27,28] using AE registration and X-ray observations of damage.

MICRO-MESO-MACRO STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Fast homogenisation with the inclusions model is well-suited to be used in micro-macro calculations. Simulation of the performance of textile composite parts takes into account variability of local properties of the composite, as a 3D-shaped textile preform undergoes shear deformations in the processing. The intensity of shear varies from point to point, changing the local properties of the composite part.

As reported in detail in [11,12], four different parts (Figure 10) was modelled with commercial CAD software packages providing a geometrical description, which was transferred to a FE mesh that is needed for further simulations (graphs below show results for woven glass/epoxy hemisphere with diameter of 400 mm)

Figure 10 Composite parts: NCF carbon/epoxy and woven glass/epoxy hemispheres, Twintex glass/PP hemisphere, Twintex motorbike mudguard

Figure 11 Draping: simulation and measurements, glass/epoxy hemisphere.

Although a kinematical draping algorithm is used and hence the material properties are not taken into account during the simulation, the prediction of the textile deformation is relatively accurate (Figure 11). The local stiffness of the parts was calculated as follows. *QuikForm* output file contains shear angles of the reinforcement in all the elements of the mesh (the difference between shear of the different layers of the preform was neglected). For each element *WiseTex* calculated the internal geometry of the sheared reinforcement. The result

was processed by *TexComp* to produce full stiffness matrix of the impregnated reinforcement in the element. This calculation accounts for the differences of the properties in elements induced by local shear: (1) fibre volume fraction; (2) in-plane orientations of the yarns and fibres inside them; (3) out-of-plane orientations of the yarns in the sheared woven structure.

The parts were tested in compression at the constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min. Care was taken to ensure that the boundary conditions correspond to rigid clamping of the part edges: they were glued to the base with epoxy glue. Local strains on the surface of the parts were registered using strain gages. FEA (*SYSPLY*) was performed using stiffness of the elements calculated with: (1) *WiseTex/TexComp*; (2) simple model based on Classical Laminate Theory and in-plane changes of the fibre orientations.

Comparison (Figure 12) between the global part behaviour (force-displacement for the whole part) during loading and the FE simulation shows a reasonable prediction of the part stiffness in the elastic region. For local strains, the ‘micro-macro modelling’ technique based on the homogenisation of a real reinforcement textile structure approaches the tested values better than a simplified model, especially in areas where textile structures are highly deformed during production (large shearing angle of the fabric), as it could be expected.

Figure 12 Experimental and calculated load-deflection curves (left) and local strains (right, 1 mm displacement of the compression head). Glass/epoxy hemisphere, 1: strain in horizontal direction; 2: strain in vertical direction. A: low shear positions, B: high shear positions

TEXTILE VIRTUAL REALITY

One of important applications of models of internal geometry is visualisation of the textile architecture. The ultimate result of visualisation of a model is the creation of a virtual reality (VR) world. Up to now, complicated textile VR is being created mostly on macro-level, displaying drape of a cloth and serving needs of garment designers and producers of animations, supported by the appeal for the wide public. Micro-level (internal structure) textile VR (below we will also use a shortened term “micro-VR”) attracts lesser attention. However, such an application is of great interest for textile education and for the popularisation of textile industry and science (e.g., interactive exhibits for industrial and science museums). It can be also used for research purposes in the same way as stereochemistry takes advantage of 3D-models of large molecules.

The *VRTex* software is a tool, which transforms a *WiseTex* data file to the virtual reality data files according to VRML standard, which can be used for any VRML browser, providing 3D visualisation, navigation and interaction facilities. VRML commands defining the VR-world are generated by *VRTex* for all the yarns and the fibrous plies in the fabric unit cell. These definitions are translated in three directions as requested by the user; VRML instruments allow doing this almost without penalty in the file size, but the user interaction time increases linearly with the enlargement of the virtual world. Figure 13 shows the usage of *VRTex*, illustrating “travelling” in the virtual world.

Figure 13 VRText: Data transfer scheme (a) and travel in textile virtual world (b)

CONCLUSION

WiseTex family of models and software provides integrated description of internal geometry and properties of textile fabrics and composites on unit cell level and is used for multilevel μ -m-M analysis. General format of description of internal geometry of textile reinforcements is open to be used in further developments

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REFERENCES

- Lomov S.V. et al, *Comp Sci Tech*, **60**, 2083, 2000
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Comp A*, **32**, 1379, 2001
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Text Res J*, **71**, 534, 2001
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Int J Form Proc*, **6**, 413, 2003
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Text Res J*, **72**, 706, 2002
- Moesen, M. et al, *Proc TechTextil*, CD, 2003
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Comp A*, **33**, 1171, 2002
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Comp Sci Tech*, **63**, 993, 2003
- Belov E. et al, *Comp Sci Tech*, **64**, 1069, 2004
- Laine B. et al, *Proc ESAFORM-6*, CD, 2005
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Proc ECCM-11*, CD, 2004
- Van den Broecke, B, et al, *Proc SAMPE-Europe*, 194, 2004
- Carvelli V. et al, *Proc ECCM-11*, CD, 2004
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Proc SAMPE-Europe*, 379, 2001
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Rev Eur Elem Finis*, in print, 2005
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Proc SAMPE-Europe*, CD, 2005
- Kurashiki T. et al, *Proc ECCM-11*, CD, 2004
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Proc TechTextil*, CD, 2005
- Lomov S.V. et al, *Text Res J*, in print, 2005
- Lomov S.V. et al, *J Reinf Plast Comp*, **19**, 1329, 2000
- Huisman G. et al, *Acta Mater*, **46**, 3003, 1998
- Huisman G. et al, *Comp A*, **32**, 1465, 2001
- Loendersloot R et al, *Comp A*, in print, 2005
- Verleye B. et al, *Proc ICAS*, CD, 2005
- Hoes K. et al, *Comp A*, **35**, 1407, 2004
- Lee, J.R. et al, *Comp A*, **35**, 849, 2004
- Truong, T.C., *Comp A*, in print, 2005
- Vettori, M., *Proc ECCM-11*, CD, 2004